

THE ROLE OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE WORLD

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Abstract: It is no secret that English is the most widely spoken the world today. This language is becoming the only language understood by the people of the world. As the number of people increases, the need for language increasing. Everyone has the official language of the nation and state, but for the people of the earth to understand each other, one language is English is the second language after Chinese. I think everyone is interested in the spread and history of English. In which countries the official and second language? You can learn about it from this article.

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The modern world is hard to imagine without English. Today it's one of the most widely spoken language in the world. This language no spoken only by resident of UK and USA, New Zealand and Australia. English is also the official language of Canada, Belize, India and other countries. English is the official language of international organizations: The UN, UNESCO, NATO. In addition, the popularity of English can also be attributed to the fact it's the language of the tourism. People planning a trip abroad and speaking English almost always sure that they will not experience difficulties in communicating with the local population.

The invention of the Internet in the UNITED STATES also contributed to the strengthening of the world. More than 75% of the cities on the Internet exist in English and communication between people from different countries around the WORLD WIDE WEB is also in English. The spread of English language in the world is inexplicably linked with the strengthening of the political and economic influence of English spoken countries throughout history. After the acquisition of economic and political independence the UNITED STATES joined the process of the spreading the English language in the world. And especially purposefully and actively propaganda of the English language began to be carried out after the SECOND WORLD WAR. Today, English is the primary language of communication for more 500 million people and second language for another 2 billion people. English is the language of commerce and business. 95% of the world's transactions are done in English. World financial funds and stocks exchanges operate in English. Large corporations use English in every corner of the world. Although English is not spoken, it is much easier for foreign investors to express their proposals in this language. English the language of education. It's mainly thought as a foreign language in schools.

The first 10 universities which are among the most prestigious universities in the world, operate in English. English comedies, movies, books and works of art are very popular among the youth of the world. American writers have taken a place in the hearts of millions of young people. In the 17th century the works of Shakespeare became extremely popular not only in England but all over the world. His work introduced many new phrases into English and marked the era of early modern English. Did you know that 90% of European schoolchildren

study English at one of time or another? But this does not mean that they speak it as fluently as adults. There are several countries and regions in Europe that primarily speak English and have English as their official language. Among them: GREAT BRITAIN, IRELAND, SCOTLAND, MALTA, WALES, GIBRALTAR. There are several countries in Asia where English is considered an official language and not even necessarily being the main language of the population. Then countries include: INDIA, PAKISTAN, PHILIPPINES, SINGAPORE. Most African countries have many official languages and even more languages and dialects are spoken in this country. Even though English is listed as the official language in these countries many people do not speak it. For example: in Namibia, only 5% of population speaks English, despite the fact that it is the only official language. In Botswana, English is the official business language but it's no spoken very often. Many people in Eritrea and Ethiopia also speak English, although it's not official language. In Australia, English is spoken by the majority of the population and is the only language used in government official, yet Australia does not have an official language. The Importance of English in the modern World. In general, scientific, sports life of the whole world in English. International trade, the operation of the banking system, the activities of the transport system on land, at sea and in the air are carried out in English. This language is a living communication tool for academicians, doctors of sciences around in the world. Knowledge of English in the modern world in a kind of window to the world. Knowing this language of international communication, you will be able to achieve your goals with the help of new opportunities. And you will definitely understand that the importance of the English language is not exaggerated. English in the world is very important for students who want to get a decent education with an international diploma. Knowledge of vocabulary and grammar opens the door to the best educational institutions upon completions of which you can country in the world. A person can work in many international companies, give private lessons English, work as a guide in any country and get many other possibilities.

Interesting facts:

1. people aged 25 30 have the best command of English.
2. Countries with high English proficiency are more democratic and more open.
3. Two years ago, women's average English proficiency was higher than men's in most countries and globally.

The gap is still there, but it has narrowed considerably. All countries are divided into 4 categories according to the level of language proficiency:

1. High
2. Medium
3. Low
4. Very Low

The inhabitants of Northern Europe turned out to be the most advanced in knowledge of English. In the countries' rank the English knowledge level is of several years already headed by the Netherlands. The latest version of the ranking was released in 2021. Of all world languages (over 2.700), English may have the richest vocabulary; The OXFORD ENGLISH DICTIONARY contains 500.000 words, and there are about half a million more scientific and technical terms not listed in dictionaries. More countries are joining the global trend of international partnerships and as a result the need for the English language is growing. According to the latest predictions of researchers, by 2023 approximately 3 billion people will learn English – both as

a foreign language as a second one. That's almost a quarter of the world population! As a result, the need for teachers, courses, textbooks are increasing, especially in countries where and the study of English is only gaining momentum. All these figures and facts for a modern person English if not necessarily, is very important. In the future its role will only increase. Remember that it's never too late to learn a foreign language, but the sooner you start the better.

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